

TEACHING THE TRANSLATION OF TERMINOLOGY OF PROFESSIONALISM

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ABSTRACT

In this article matter is about to act sequence by learning special and technical text. Learn Foreign language apply for forming communicative competence educability to Foreign language, as well intercultural competence. By force of foreign language become professional foreign language.

Introduction. Modern technological innovations involve a radical change in the educational paradigm, the orientation of interethnic dialogue to practical needs and the formation of pedagogical concepts in accordance with the laws of intercultural dialogue, the only way to achieve this is the foreign language itself. Thus, the study of a foreign language implies the development of communicative competence - the ability to communicate in another language, which is necessary for intercultural communication.

Therefore, it is becoming a specialty, even a professional language. The realization of this goal of foreign language teaching is not only related to the development of intercultural communication skills, understood as communication between participants of

different national cultures in the context of globalization, it is not only a tool and key to the new world information flow way too.

Literature review. Today, the development and advancement of science requires the training of future engineers, including technical staff, in foreign language training, primarily on the basis of the formation of linguocultural competence. The formation of linguoculturological competence of future specialists in the field of agriculture, the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in a foreign language will provide them with practical assistance in solving communicative problems in their professional activities.

In the article, we found it appropriate to pay more attention to technical terms and texts, some words that are common in the field of irrigation. Such

an approach is necessary to learn from future foreign experts with advanced experience of highly developed quality of education, as well as the adoption of technical literature, all regulatory documents in the field of irrigation in pure language.

Research Methodology. It should be noted that in the context of Uzbekistan, we face some problems when learning / teaching a foreign language at a technical university. These include:

- Lack of diversity among students studying in the faculties of professional specialties;
- systematic and meaningless inconsistency in the development of communicative competence in the professional direction, the study of a foreign language in the context of a non-philological university;
- alternative communicative professional orientation, clear level of education should be continuous;
- the expediency of teaching a foreign language not only in the course, but also throughout the school year.

Intercultural communication is characterized by many aspects. In mastering the components of linguoculturological competence in intercultural communication in a foreign language, the system of knowledge of the foreign language taught by the language learner is fourfold in the formation of their native language interpretation, knowledge and skills in intercultural communication.

Therefore, the previous interpretation of foreign language communication, which leads only to the intuitive acquisition of a foreign language, is absolutely insufficient in today's globalization, innovative development of

the economy and the expansion of the information space of society. This means that teaching students in different fields of science and technology should be done synchronously and practically, as well as in close connection with culture, because cognitively language units are characterized by interaction with concepts and linguistic and cultural specificity, i.e. by teaching English we culture and language.

Analysis and results. One of the tasks of teaching a foreign language as a science in non-philological higher education institutions is not only to develop the skills of understanding the scientific literature, but also the formation of communicative competence. Among the basic skills required for independent work with technical texts, translation of terms in the field of non-philological education of higher education institutions, we have included the following, and based on this, a model of developing linguoculturological competence of students of non-philological specialties was created.

Communicative competence in a foreign language reflects the complex structural aspects of the individual with integrative qualities in future irrigation professionals. It consists of three components:

- Motivational expression (preparation for interest in the profession he is studying and understanding of its importance in the future);
- combining cognitive activity (foreign language) with communicative competence within the scope of professional activity;
- general interdisciplinary competence (one of the methods of free-voluntary self-assessment in future professional activities, combining the

importance of the quality of knowledge and skills of future engineers in the field of irrigation) was used cluster method.

In the lingvosotsium of foreign norms is used as a means of language, that is, the translation of terms. A term is a word or phrase of a particular science, social field, or technical unit concept. The concept of the term should be clear and concise, their scope is very wide, there are specific terms in agriculture, irrigation, medicine, engineering, metallurgy, aerospace, computer science, linguistics, pharmaceuticals, politics, sports, culture and others. According to some data, the modern system of terms consists of more than one million units.

The main ones are:

- ability to understand the general content of reading;
- the ability to identify in the text a sentence (basic terminological word or basic phrase) that reflects the object and purpose of the idea (sentence);

- ability to distinguish the characteristics of the object of the sentence using terminological words in the text.

Conclusion/Recommendations. In the process of forming the professional activity of students of non-philological higher education in a foreign language, the general basic basis and specialization competence and professional competence in a "foreign language" serve as education in a technological context. In the field of activity, a foreign language is studied as a type of speech activity, such as speaking, listening comprehension, reading, writing, translation. Communicating in a foreign language is a major educational task, hence the name communicative approach (method). The role of verbal activity is carried out in the form of games, problem situations, free communication. Professional vocabulary or professionalism serves terms related to the professional, such as terms.

REFERENCES:

1. Johnson, K. E. The Sociocultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., – London., 2006: – 235- bet.
2. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. – London., 2001: – 64-bet.
3. Jalolov J. Chet tili o'qitish metodikasi. – Toshkent., 2012: – 48-bet.
4. Khakimova, K. B. (2020). THE SUBJECT AND PLACE OF TOPONYMICS IN THE SYSTEM OF SCIENCES. *Science and Education*, 1 (Special Issue 2).
5. Gazieva, S. T. (2020). MODERN TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Academic Research in Educational Sciences*, 1 (3), 1272-1275.
6. Khakimova, K. B. (2020). BASIC PRINCIPLES OF CONVERSATION OF TOPONYMS ON GEOGRAPHIC MAPS. *Scientific-methodical journal of SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS*, (Volume 1, Issue 4, February 2021).